

Separation of the effect of solvent on the oxidation of 3-R-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones by QCC in partial aqueous medium into contributions to initial and transition states

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The kinetics of oxidation of 3-R-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones (where, R = H and Me) by quinolinium chlorochromate have been studied under pseudo-first order conditions in aqueous 1,4-dioxane mixtures of varying compositions. The rate data are correlated with different solvent parameters using linear multiple regression analysis. From the results, information on the solvent-reactants and the solvent-transition state interactions is obtained.

A survey of literature shows that the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of substituted 2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones by various oxidants is well understood¹⁻³. Kinetic investigations of redox reactions in aqueous organic solvents and correlation of the reaction rates with various solvent parameters would provide important information regarding the mechanism of such reactions. The objective of the present work, therefore, is to study the title reaction in aqueous 1,4-dioxane mixtures of varying compositions, to check the utility of such solvent variation studies in the interpretation of mechanism and, in particular, to separate the effect of solvent on the title reaction into contributions to initial and transition states.

Results and Discussion

The observed pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for different volume fractions of the added organic cosolvent are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants ($10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$, s^{-1}) for the oxidation of 3-R-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones by QCC in aqueous 1,4-dioxane mixtures at 25°

[Substrate] = 1×10^{-2} M, [QCC] = 1×10^{-3} M, [H⁺] = 5×10^{-1} M

R	1,4-Dioxane % (v/v)						
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
H	0.81	1.07	2.04	4.01	4.39	8.27	11.60
Me	0.78	1.05	1.34	1.48	1.98	3.17	3.80

The solvent effect was analyzed using the Grunwald-Winstein equation⁴:

$$\log k = \log k_0 + mY$$

where Y is an empirical parameter (solvent ionizing power)

characteristic of the given solvent and m is a substrate parameter measuring the substrate sensitivity to changes in the ionizing power of the medium. For both the compounds, a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs Y is linear (for R = H piperidone, $r = 0.979$, $\text{sd} = 0.097$, $\text{slope} = -0.364$; for R = Me piperidone, $r = 0.991$, $\text{sd} = 0.037$, $\text{slope} = -0.212$) with negative slopes. The negative value of m points to a transition state which is less polar than the reactants⁵. Such a transition state will more easily be attained in a medium of lower ionizing power and hence the increase in rate with increase in amount of organic cosolvent added.

No single macroscopic physical parameter could possibly account for the multitude of solute-solvent interactions on the molecular microscopic level. Thus, bulk solvent properties like the solvent ionizing power will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of transition state and hence the rate of the reaction. Swain *et al.*⁶ believed that, in relation to specific solvation, the important properties of the solvent affecting the chemical reactivity are their anion solvating tendency (A) and cation solvating tendency (B). Thus the observed kinetic data were analyzed in terms of Swain's Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER):

$$\log k = a A + b B + c$$

The rates of oxidation for both the compounds investigated show excellent correlation in the above LSER.

For R = H piperidone,

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -4.407 A + 0.369 B + 7.6 \times 10^{-4}$$

($N = 7$, $R = 0.998$, $R^2 = 0.997$, $\text{sd} = 0.114$, $P_A = 92$ and $P_B = 8$)

For R = Me piperidone,

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -1.954 A + 1.614 B - 0.528$$

$$(N = 7, R = 0.991, R^2 = 0.981, \text{sd} = 0.042, \\ P_A = 55 \text{ and } P_B = 45)$$

Such an excellent correlation indicates the existence of specific local electrostatic solute-solvent interactions. For both the compounds the anion solvating tendency plays a major role. The negative sign of the coefficient of A term shows that the specific interaction between the reactants and the solvent is more than that between the transition state and the solvent. Further, the rate of the reaction will increase with decrease in anion solvating tendency of the solvent.

In order to obtain a deeper insight into the specific and non-specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions which influence the reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet *et al.*⁷ This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. The kinetic data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* characteristic of the different mixtures in the form of LSER,

$$\log k = A_0 + s \pi^* + a \alpha + b \beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The rates of oxidation for both the compounds studied show excellent correlations with solvent via the above LSER.

For $R = \text{H}$ piperidone,

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = 193.34 - 287.52 \pi^* + 113.86 \alpha + 95.63 \beta \\ (N = 7, R = 0.991, R^2 = 0.981, \text{sd} = 0.085, \\ P_{\pi^*} = 58, P_{\alpha} = 23 \text{ and } P_{\beta} = 19)$$

For $R = \text{Me}$ piperidone,

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = 6.38 - 58.67 \pi^* + 35.75 \alpha + 64.76 \beta \\ (N = 7, R = 0.990, R^2 = 0.980, \text{sd} = 0.054, \\ P_{\pi^*} = 37, P_{\alpha} = 22 \text{ and } P_{\beta} = 41)$$

The observation of this systematic multiple regression analysis leads us to the following preliminary conclusions. (i) The contribution of the solvent dipolarity/polarizability (π^*) to the total solvent effect is predominant. The negative sign of the coefficient of this term indicates that the reactant

solvation by the solvent mixture is extensive. Furthermore, it indicates that the rate of oxidation will increase with decrease in dipolarity/polarizability of the medium. Since 1,4-dioxane is a less polar solvent, increase in its mole fraction in the mixture may stabilize the transition state (which is less polar than the reactants) and consequently increase in the rate of oxidation. (ii) The solvent HBA basicity also plays an appreciable role. The transition state is solvated extensively through HBA interactions than the reactants as indicated by the positive sign of the coefficient of this term. Since 1,4-dioxane is a typical HBA solvent, the increase in its mole fraction in the mixture may stabilize the transition state through HBA interaction and consequently increases the rate of the reaction. (iii) The rate of the reaction is also influenced by solvent HBD property. The positive sign of this coefficient suggests that the transition state is extensively solvated by the solvent mixture than the reactants, through HBD interactions.

To conclude, decrease in polarity and anion solvating tendency of the medium or increase in solvent HBA property of the medium will stabilize the transition state and consequently increases the rate of the reaction.

Experimental

The procedure adopted for the preparation of 3-*R*-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones ($R = \text{H}$ and Me) was essentially same as that of Baliah and Noller⁸. Quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC) was prepared by reported method⁹ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of the substrate over QCC. The progress of the reactions was followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$. The rate constants were determined by least-squares method from the linear plots of $\log [\text{QCC}]$ vs time. Duplicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The stoichiometry and product analysis were carried out as reported earlier^{1,2}. Correlation analysis were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 3.5) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r), standard deviation (sd) and coefficient of multiple determination (R^2). The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹.

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